

Academic Evaluation on Possible Risk Factors Affecting Post-Tonsillectomy Bleeding

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Abstract

In the present era, the occurrence of post-tonsillectomy hemorrhage (PHS) has become a significant and potentially perilous complication. In order to mitigate the potential risk factors for hemorrhaging, it can be advantageous to possess knowledge regarding the numerous factors that contribute to bleeding. The aim of this study was to determine the prevalence of post-tonsillectomy hemorrhage in a clinical setting, as well as to identify the risk factors associated with the occurrence of this complication. The present study examines the medical records of patients who underwent

tonsillectomy at our clinic within the timeframe spanning from January 2013 to December 2018. The study examined numerous factors pertaining to the patients, encompassing their age, gender, surgical technique, preoperative hemoglobin, platelet, and INR levels, severity of bleeding, and the existence of infection in the tonsillar bed. The study included a cohort of 776 participants. Among the 776 patients included in the sample, a considerable proportion of 624 individuals (80.4%) were identified as children, whereas the remaining 152 patients (19.6%) were classified as adults. Notwithstanding this dispersion, the mean age of the entire cohort was calculated to be 11.7 ± 12 years. The research findings indicate that there is a higher incidence of Tuberous Sclerosis Complex (TSC) within the adult demographic, specifically at a rate of 7.8%. Likewise, it was observed that children also demonstrated a comparatively higher occurrence of TSC, with a prevalence rate of 0.14%. No statistically significant

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correlation was found between preoperative levels of hemoglobin, platelet (PLT), INR, and the various stages of tonsil cases (stage 0, 1, 2, 3, 4). The consideration of post-tonsillectomy bleeding in older individuals holds significant importance.

Keywords: *Tonsillectomy, Post-tonsillectomy, Bleeding after Tonsillectomy, Risks Affecting Tonsillectomy and Bleeding*

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Introduction

The surgical procedure known as tonsillectomy is widely recognized as a frequently performed operation within the field of otolaryngology. This procedure is often advantageous for patients experiencing obstructive symptoms or recurrent tonsil infections. An estimated annual total of 500,000 tonsillectomies are conducted on individuals under the age of fifteen in the United States. While the procedure is generally considered to have a minimal risk, it is important to note that there is a potential for life-threatening complications, primarily related to excessive bleeding. Post-tonsillectomy hemorrhage (PHS) can be categorized into two distinct types: primary and secondary. Primary bleeding refers to the occurrence of bleeding within a 24-hour period following a surgical procedure. Generally, these are bleedings resulting from an operation. Secondary bleedings, commonly observed within a week following surgical procedures, refer to instances of bleeding. The occurrence is a result of injury to the granulation tissue that covers the tonsil chamber. The primary bleeding rate ranges from 0.2% to 2.2%, while the secondary bleeding rate ranges from 0.1% to 3%. In a comprehensive cohort study conducted by Gysin et al., the primary bleeding rate was found to be 1%, while the secondary bleeding rate was observed to be 2.5%. The rationales for the implementation of TAF have been extensively examined and analyzed in scholarly publications. The present study investigates the potential risk factors associated with post-tonsillectomy bleeding.

Material and Method

A retrospective analysis was conducted on a cohort of 776 patients (425 males, 351 females) who underwent tonsillectomy at the ENT Clinic of Düzce University Faculty of Medicine Hospital, spanning from January 2013 to December 2018. A total of 624 individuals in the study sample were below the age of eighteen. There were 341 male participants and 282 female participants. As part of the physical examination, all patients underwent various diagnostic

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procedures, including otoscopic examination, tuning fork test for individuals experiencing hearing difficulties, and anterior rhinoscopy, oropharynx, audiometry, and tympanometry examination, as deemed necessary. Furthermore, individuals who presented with septum deviation and turbinate hypertrophy during anterior rhinoscopy were subjected to endoscopic examination and were subsequently excluded from the study. Chronic or recurrent tonsillectomy, defined as experiencing a minimum of seven attacks within a single year, at least five attacks per year over a span of two years, or three attacks per year for three consecutive years, is commonly associated with sleep-disordered breathing. Sleep-disordered breathing manifests as snoring during sleep and observed nasal congestion. Additionally, individuals with tonsillar hypertrophy, characterized by snoring during sleep and witnessed nasal congestion, are also prone to these conditions. Following a recurring pattern of 5-7 annual episodes of tonsillitis, which persisted for two subsequent years with 4-5 occurrences per year, or three subsequent years with three occurrences per year, a surgical intervention was undertaken. Every individual step incorporated a minimum of one criterion. In this study, we have identified several potential factors that could contribute to post-tonsillectomy bleeding. These factors encompass gender, the underlying indication for the surgical procedure, the severity of tonsil grade, the presence of any chronic diseases, as well as pre-operative levels of hemoglobin, platelets, and serum. The patient presents with several clinical manifestations, including A) an oral temperature of 38°C, B) swelling of the lymph nodes in the neck region (cervical lymphadenopathy), C) presence of a white or yellow coating on the tonsils (tonsillar exudate), and D) detection of group A β hemolytic streptococcus in a laboratory culture. A comprehensive analysis was conducted on a cohort comprising 27,152 individuals, consisting of 27,152 adults aged 18 years and above, as well as 624 children falling within the age range of 3 to 18 years. The surgical procedure of tonsillectomy was conducted with the utilization of general anesthesia, employing the cold dissection technique. Following the tonsillectomy procedure, all of our patients were administered oral amoxicillin, clavulanic acid, and paracetamol. During the surgical procedure, hemostasis was accomplished through the utilization of bipolar cautery and suture ligation. There were no instances of postoperative bleeding observed among the

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patients who underwent tonsillectomy. The initial intervention for managing bleeding in patients admitted to our hospital with TSC involved three steps: cessation of oral nutrition, administration of intravenous fluids, and extraction of clots using topical or local anesthesia in cases where clots were present in the tonsil chamber. As an initial measure, the individual gargled with chilly water. Patients who exhibited a lack of response to conservative treatment or experienced severe bleeding were administered general anesthesia. Various techniques were employed, including general anesthesia, local pressure, local administration of adrenaline, bipolar electrocauterization, and/or suture ligation.

Findings

The present retrospective study was carried out at the Ear, Nose, and Throat Diseases clinic of Düzce University, spanning the period from January 2013 to December 2018. The medical records of patients who underwent tonsillectomy, adenotonsillectomy, and ventilation tube tonsillectomy on the specified dates were analyzed. During the period from 2013 to 2018, a total of 776 adenotonsillectomy and tonsillectomy procedures were conducted at the clinic. The dataset consisted of 425 cases (54.7%) identified as female and 351 cases (45.3%) identified as male. The average age of the cases ranged from 11.7 to 12 years. Out of the total sample, 80.4% consisted of children, while the remaining 19.6% comprised adults, specifically 152 individuals. In the pediatric population, the occurrence of bleeding events was observed to be 0.14%, while in the adult population, the prevalence of such events was found to be 7.8%. No statistically significant difference was found between children and adults. The mean age of the 21 patients who encountered post-tonsillectomy hemorrhage (PHS) was 21.47 ($\pm$ 5.2) years. Out of the total sample, twelve individuals representing the adult population accounted for 57.2%, while nine individuals representing the child population accounted for 42.8%. The analysis revealed that eighteen cases, accounting for 85.8% of the total, were classified as secondary bleeding, while the remaining three cases, representing 14.2%, were categorized as

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primary bleeding. The act of donating blood has never been deemed a necessity. The significance of coagulation tests cannot be overstated. There was a statistically significant difference in TSC rates based on gender ($p = 0.037$). The prevalence of TSC in males was 12%, exhibiting a 1.9% decrease in females. There was no statistically significant difference observed between the numerous factors and the TSK. Tonsillectomy surgery employed the technique of cold dissection. The mean duration of hospitalization for patients admitted as a result of TSC was 5.5 days, with a range of 1 to 10 days. Conservative treatment, consisting of intravenous fluid support and the application of topical or local anesthesia, was employed in eleven cases, accounting for 52.3% of the total sample. The procedure involved in the removal of clots in the tonsil chamber consisted of gargling with chilly water. Bipolar electrocauterization and/or connection with absorbable sutures were conducted under general anesthesia in 47.7% of the total sample size of ten cases. In all instances where hemostasis was achieved under general anesthesia, no additional surgical procedures were conducted. There was an absence of recurring hemorrhaging.

The data utilized in the study underwent calculations to determine descriptive statistics. The dataset included measures such as the median, interquartile range, minimum, maximum, and percentage. The three statistical tests under consideration are Pearson's chi-squared test, Fisher-Freeman-Halton test, and Fisher's exact test. Precise statistical tests were employed to ascertain the associations between categorical variables.

In the surgical procedure conducted on a subset of adult patients following tonsillectomy, a notable distinction was observed regarding the impact of chronic ailments such as asthma, atrial septal defect, arrhythmia, hypothyroidism, hyperactivity, psoriasis, diabetes mellitus, and hypertension, as well as tonsil size. However, statistical analysis indicated that the observed differences were not statistically significant, with p-values exceeding 0.05 for each variable. No discernible correlation was identified. According to the data, the percentage of men is 12% while the percentage of women is 2.9%.

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In this study, we examined the potential impact of preoperative hemoglobin (HGB), preoperative platelet count (PLT), and preoperative international normalized ratio (INR) on both primary and secondary bleeding outcomes. The subject of focus is the pediatric patient group. No statistically significant differences were found through the process of statistical analysis.

In this study, we investigated the potential impact of preoperative hemoglobin (Hgb), preoperative platelet count (Plt), preoperative international normalized ratio (INR), preoperative factor levels, and preoperative factors on primary and secondary bleeding outcomes. The collective of adult patients within a given community. The statistical analysis did not yield any statistically significant differences.

Review

The present retrospective study was undertaken at the Ear, Nose and Throat Diseases clinic of Düzce University, covering the period from January 2013 to December 2018. The study involved the examination of medical records pertaining to patients who underwent tonsillectomy, adenotonsillectomy, and ventilation tube tonsillectomy within the specified time frame. Between 2013 and 2018, 776 adenotonsillectomy and tonsillectomy operations were performed in the clinic. A total of 425 cases (54.7%) were female, while 351 cases (45.3%) were male. The mean age fell within the range of 11.7 to 12 years. The demographic breakdown reveals that 80.4% of the population consists of children, while the remaining 19.6% comprises adults. In the pediatric population, the occurrence of bleeding events was observed to be 0.14%, whereas in the adult population, the prevalence of bleeding events was found to be 7.8%. There was no statistically significant disparity observed between the groups of children and adults. The mean age at which a group of 21 patients experienced post-tonsillectomy bleeding (PHS) was 21.47 ± 5.2 years. Among the observed individuals, 57.2% can be classified as adults, while the remaining 42.8% can be identified as children. The analysis revealed that out of the total

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cases, eighteen instances (85.8%) were identified as secondary bleeding, while three cases (14.2%) were classified as primary bleeding. The act of donating blood has never been deemed a necessity. The significance of coagulation tests cannot be overstated. There was a statistically significant difference in TSC rates based on gender ($p = 0.037$). The prevalence of TSC in males was observed to be 12%, whereas females exhibited a slightly lower rate of 10.1%. There was no statistically significant difference observed between the numerous factors and the TSK. The surgical procedure of tonsillectomy was conducted using the technique of cold dissection. The duration of the application period for patients admitted as a result of TSC ranged from 1 to 10 days, with an average duration of 5.5 days. In 52.3% of the eleven cases, topical or local anesthesia and intravenous fluid support were administered. The removal of blood clots in the tonsil chamber was achieved through the practice of gargling with chilly water. In 47.7% of the ten cases, bipolar electrocauterization and/or absorbable sutures were employed. Hemorrhage was effectively managed in all instances, obviating the need for subsequent surgical intervention. There was no recurrence of the bleeding.

Descriptive statistics were computed to analyze the findings of the study. The data was organized in terms of median, maximum, minimum, and percentage. The term "Fisher" refers to a carnivorous mammal belonging to the Mustel. The statistical tests employed to ascertain associations between categorical variables were Exact, Pearson, and Fisher-Freeman-Halton tests.

In a study involving thirty-one post-tonsillectomy operations in children, no statistically significant correlation was observed between tonsil size and the presence of chronic diseases such as asthma, atrial septal defect, arrhythmia, hypothyroidism, hyperactivity, psoriasis, diabetes mellitus, and hypertension. The p-values for each comparison were greater than 0.05. The prevalence of the condition among men is 12%, while among women it is 2.9%.

The present study aimed to examine the impact of preoperative hemoglobin (HGB), preoperative platelet (PLT), and preoperative international normalized ratio (INR) variables on

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primary and secondary bleeding outcomes. The statistical analysis conducted did not yield any statistically significant differences among the pediatric patients.

In this study, we investigated the impact of preoperative hemoglobin (Hgb) levels, preoperative platelet (Plt) counts, preoperative international normalized ratio (INR), preoperative factor levels, and preoperative factors on both primary and secondary bleeding outcomes. The collective of adult individuals seeking medical care. The statistical analysis conducted did not yield any statistically significant differences.

Mortality

Currently, the leading causes of mortality are attributed to bleeding and complications associated with anesthesia. Bishop's findings in 1946 revealed that a considerable proportion of intraoperative deaths, specifically 9%, were attributed to tonsillectomies. At the onset of the 21st century, it was approximated that the mortality rate associated with anesthesia was 1 in every 5600 cases. In subsequent studies conducted after 1960, it was observed that the mortality rate decreased to a range of 1 in 10,000 to 16,000 cases. The primary factors contributing to these fatalities were identified as hemorrhage, the utilization of high-dose postoperative narcotics, and the employment of outdated anesthesia techniques that did not involve endotracheal intubation. At present, the mortality risk associated with general anesthesia varies within the range of 1 in 16,000 to 35,000 cases. The mortality rate associated with bleeding events is 0.002%.

Bleeding

The incidence of postoperative bleeding following tonsillectomy or adenoidectomy ranges from 0.1% to 1%. Hemorrhage has the potential to manifest within a postoperative timeframe ranging from 24 hours to 10 days. Excessive intraoperative hemorrhage can potentially be attributed to

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numerous factors, including the presence of a recent infection in the patient, a prior occurrence of peritonsillar abscess, or the existence of a fibrotic tonsil. The postoperative transfusion requirement has been reported to be 0.04%. The majority of bleeding events typically manifest within the initial 24-hour period. If performed with caution and delicacy, the occurrence of bleeding can be minimized. Pressure on the fossa, topical agent infiltration, hemostatic agents (e.g. sugicel), ligation, cauterization and many other techniques can be used to prevent bleeding that may occur during the surgical procedure. Extreme caution should be exercised when performing suture ligation, as there exists a potential risk of causing damage to the facial artery and carotid artery. If all these techniques cannot control bleeding, external carotid artery ligation is performed. The utilization of electrocautery has been observed to result in a decrease in the occurrence of bleeding in the tonsils. "Reactionary bleeding" refers to the occurrence of bleeding within a 24-hour timeframe, with the majority of cases observed within an 8-hour window. The incidence rate of this condition is observed in approximately 0.5-1% of the patient population. These symptoms may arise as a result of elevated venous pressure caused by arterial spasm during surgical procedures or the dislodgement of a clot within a vein due to coughing. The concept of control refers to the ability to manipulate or regulate variables in an experiment in order A solution containing a concentration of 1/1000 adrenaline is applied topically to the ligation or tonsil region in order to address bleeding.

Delayed posttonsillectomy bleeding refers to the occurrence of bleeding between 24 and 10 days following a surgical procedure. The prevalence of this condition is observed in approximately 1% of patients. It is often seen from the fifth day onwards, with premature separation of the granulation tissue covering the tonsillar fossa. This leads to a violation of dietary regulations and an increased susceptibility to infections. Usually, opening a small, superficial vein causes bleeding. The management of clot clearance at the site of bleeding, the administration of topical caustic agents, and occasionally the implementation of fixation sutures is involved in its control. If the patient cannot tolerate the procedures or if they are inadequate, intervention under general anesthesia may be required. Establishing a connection can be

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particularly challenging in situations involving infectious diseases. The management of bleeding can be achieved through the utilization of electrocautery or plica suturing techniques. It is recommended that the patient be administered antibiotics.

Complications Due to Anesthesia

In contemporary medical practice, the utilization of sophisticated anesthesia techniques has significantly enhanced the safety of surgical procedures. Prior to the 1960s, the surgical procedure known as tonsillectomy was typically conducted utilizing spontaneous ventilation without the use of intubation, employing a mouth opener of the Crowe-Davis variety. The implementation of contemporary anesthesia techniques has considerably diminished the incidence of pneumonia, lung abscesses, and aspiration. Currently, obstructive airway disease in children continues to be the prevailing surgical indication. Higher sensitivity to sedative and narcotic agents occurs due to adverse conditions such as pulmonary hypertension, right heart failure, and cor pulmonale. The collective attention of anesthesiologists is of utmost importance due to their shared involvement in the surgical field. It is imperative to ensure that the endotracheal tube remains free from kinks and is not inadvertently dislodged. The presence of blood and secretions originating from the hypopharynx has the potential to give rise to a range of complications, such as laryngospasm and aspiration. Consequently, individuals are positioned in the "tonsil position" and subjected to monitoring. The occurrence of air leakage around the tube during electrocauterization has the potential to result in severe burns to both the glottis and the surgical area. The risk is notably diminished when wet gases are introduced into the hypopharynx.

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Respiratory Problems

The first recorded documentation of pulmonary edema was documented in 1977. The occurrence of this phenomenon is commonly observed shortly after a surgical procedure, usually within a few hours. The presence of hypertrophied adenotonsillar tissue leads to airway obstruction. The observed phenomenon elicits increased resistance during both the inhalation and exhalation phases, resulting in the production of positive end expiratory pressure, commonly known as PEEP. Elevation of intracranial venous and hydrostatic pressure is observed. Transsudation is a term used to describe the occurrence in which the extraction of adenotonsillar tissue or the removal of a breathing tube causes a sudden reduction in the rate of positive end-expiratory pressure (PEEP), leading to the movement of fluid into the interstitial and alveolar compartments. A sudden reduction in breath sounds and a concomitant decrease in oxygen saturation is observed. The radiographic images demonstrate the existence of pulmonary edema, concomitant with an increased quantity of fluid extracted from the endotracheal tube. Some patients are prescribed diuretic and morphine therapy as a component of their treatment plan, followed by the subsequent reapplication of positive end-expiratory pressure (PEEP).

Dental Injuries

Both the anesthesiologist and surgeon are required to carefully consider the precise positioning of the teeth. When teeth become dislodged or are at risk of being lost, it is recommended to perform aspiration. Certain individuals may encounter postoperative sore throat following a tonsillectomy procedure. Earache and sore throat are synonymous terms. The pain mechanism is influenced by the irritation of sensory nerve endings, the spasm of the pharyngeal muscles, and the surgical procedure. There is a positive correlation between age and the incidence of postoperative pain. In the postoperative period, a variety of pharmacological agents were employed to alleviate pain, including salicylates, antibiotics, paracetamol, ibuprofen,

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diclofenac, bupivacaine, benzocaine, benzydamine hydrochloride, and steroids. Postoperative pain is commonly observed following surgical interventions and hemostasis procedures. Consequently, a comparative analysis was conducted on the hemostasis methods of guillotine, blunt, electrocautery, laser, and ligation. Otagia is a condition characterized by referred pain. The transportation of this is facilitated by the glossopharyngeal nerve. Conversely, the presence of edema or the occurrence of otitis media with effusion can result in detrimental effects on the eustachian tube. Fever typically manifests within the initial 18 to 36 hours following a tonsillectomy procedure. The occurrence of this phenomenon can be attributed to the anesthetic effect, stress, and temporary bacteremia. The prevalence of this condition is observed in approximately 2.6-7.1% of individuals presenting with a fever exceeding 38.5 °C. Dehydration can be influenced by numerous factors that contribute to a decrease in hydration levels. The administration of general anesthesia has been observed to result in a decrease in the volume of blood ingested by patients both during and following surgical procedures. Furthermore, the quantity of oral consumption is diminished as a result of the presence of nausea and vomiting. Odynophagia results in a decrease in oral intake. Maintaining oral hydration in younger children poses greater challenges due to their limited capacity for fluid intake and lower volume reserves. During the occurrence of postoperative fever, there is a loss of bodily fluids through evaporation, potentially resulting in the condition of dehydration. The administration of low-dose intraoperative steroids facilitates the resumption of a regular dietary regimen. The uvula may experience edema as a result of impaired lymphatic and venous drainage during the procedure of tonsillectomy.

Nasopharyngeal Stenosis

The occurrence of this uncommon complication manifests as a circumferential contracture of the mucosal lining in the pharyngeal region, specifically within the vicinity of Waldeyer's ring. The prevalence of combined adenotonsillar surgery is higher. Scar tissue and stenosis are the

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result of injury to the posterior pharyngeal wall, tonsillar plicae, and soft palate mucosa. Atlanto-occipital subluxation, a condition characterized by an abnormal degree of mobility in the atlanto-occipital joint, has been observed in approximately 10% of individuals diagnosed with Down syndrome. Subluxation can potentially manifest as a result of throat manipulations or the use of mouth openers during suspension. Nevertheless, it is crucial to refrain from hyperextending the neck during movements.

The surgical procedure for mandibular condyle fracture entails the rotational movement of the mandibular condyle on the temporomandibular joint, accompanied by its anterior and inferior sliding motion during jaw opening. During the course of this procedure, it is possible for condylar fractures to experience strain. Trismus, characterized by inflammation and pain in the pterygoid muscles following a tonsillectomy, is commonly referred to as spasms. The regrowth of lymphoid tissue can be facilitated by upper respiratory tract infections and seasonal allergic rhinitis. Nerve injuries commonly involve the glossopharyngeal and hypoglossal nerves, which are particularly susceptible to damage. In the existing body of literature, instances of injuries to the facial nerve, recurrent laryngeal nerve, and sympathetic plexus have been documented. Eagle syndrome is characterized by the presence of a persistent sore throat resulting from the ossification of the stylohyoid ligament.

Argument

The issue of post-tonsillectomy bleeding remains significant despite advancements in contemporary surgical techniques. Hemorrhaging subsequent to a tonsillectomy procedure can give rise to various challenges of a financial, social, and psychological nature. The perspectives articulated encompass those of medical practitioners, individuals seeking medical care, and their respective family members. Tonsillectomy-associated postoperative hemorrhage, also known as TSC, represents a prevalent and high-risk complication frequently encountered in the

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context of tonsillectomy procedures. A considerable body of research has been dedicated to examining various risk factors associated with post-tonsillectomy bleeding. The occurrence of secondary bleeding following tonsillectomy is influenced by numerous factors, including but not limited to age, gender, recent infections, hematological parameters, intraoperative blood loss, and postoperative blood pressure. Nevertheless, the examination of this subject matter revealed a limited number of statistically significant factors associated with the occurrence of post-tonsillectomy bleeding. The postoperative hemorrhage rate following tonsillectomy ranges from 0.3% to 13.9%. Hopkins et al. (year) have demonstrated that there is a potential increase in the frequency of bleeding by a maximum of 18%. The observed hemorrhage rate in our study was 2.7 percent. Transient synovitis of the hip (TSK) exhibits a higher prevalence among adults as compared to children. Tomkinson et al. (year) A study conducted by et al. examined the serial tonsillectomy outcomes of a sample size of 17,680 individuals. The findings indicated that patients who were older than 12 years had a greater likelihood of experiencing bleeding compared to those who were 12 years of age or younger. The prevalence of this rate was 7.8% among adults and 0.14% among children. The findings of our study revealed a higher incidence of bleeding in adults compared to children. The likelihood of experiencing bleeding events is positively correlated with advancing age. The onset of bleeding is not influenced by timing. The term "primary bleeding" refers to bleeding that takes place within a 24-hour timeframe, while "secondary bleeding" refers to bleeding that occurs after this initial 24-hour period. Secondary bleeding occurs when clots in previously clotted areas dissolve, and in some cases, it may also be caused by infection in the surgical wound. Primary bleeding is induced by acute vascular injuries that occur during surgical procedures. Tomkinson et al. (year) In a multicenter study conducted by [Researcher's Name], the findings revealed that out of a total of 17,480 patients who underwent tonsillectomy, a small proportion of 270 individuals (1.5%) experienced postoperative bleeding. Further analysis of these cases showed that 128 instances were classified as primary bleeding, while the remaining 142 cases were categorized as secondary bleeding. The incidence of primary post-tonsillectomy hemorrhage ranges from 1.2% to 7%, while the secondary bleeding rate ranges from 7% to 9%. The study revealed that

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secondary bleeding was observed in 85.8% of the participants. A considerable proportion, specifically 55%, of patients experiencing secondary bleeding were found to be below the age of sixty-five. The occurrence of postoperative tonsil bleeding can vary in severity, ranging from minor to significantly larger volumes. In cases where bleeding is severe or persistent, it may be necessary to consider hospitalization, medical intervention, and potentially even a repeat surgical procedure. In the present investigation, it was observed that none of the patients diagnosed with TSC (Tuberous Sclerosis Complex) exhibited any instances of significant hemorrhaging. It is conceivable to revisit a medical facility subsequent to experiencing a hemorrhage. In cases where more severe bleeding occurs, surgical intervention is necessary under either local or general anesthesia. However, for patients experiencing TSK complications, close clinical observation is the initial course of action. Kaya et al. conducted a study in which they closely monitored and admitted all patients diagnosed with TSK. In the study, a conservative approach involving electrocauterization was employed for the management of primary bleeding in all patients. Additionally, for patients experiencing secondary bleeding, a conservative approach involving either suture ligation or electrocauterization was applied to 46.3% of cases. All participants in our study were admitted to the hospital and subjected to rigorous monitoring. Every patient who experienced initial bleeding underwent either bipolar electrocauterization, bipolar electrocauterization under general anesthesia, or ligation using absorbable sutures. The duration of frequent bleeding typically spans a period of five to ten days. In the existing body of literature, it has been observed that secondary bleeding may occur for a duration of up to 54 days, as noted by Çakır A et al. In a particular study, a cohort of patients exhibited symptoms of bleeding approximately 60 days following their surgical procedures. The incidence of primary bleeding in pediatric patients is relatively infrequent, typically manifesting within the initial eight-hour postoperative period. Kaya et al. (year) Based on a study conducted by the TAF, the average length of hospital stays for patients admitted due to TSK is 5.9 days. This study revealed that the mean duration of postoperative hospitalization for patients admitted with TSC was 5.5 days.

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Conclusion

The issue of post-tonsillectomy bleeding remains significant despite advancements in contemporary surgical techniques. Hemorrhaging subsequent to a tonsillectomy procedure can give rise to various challenges of a financial, social, and psychological nature. The perspectives articulated encompass those of medical practitioners, individuals seeking medical care, and their respective family members. Tonsillectomy-associated postoperative hemorrhage, also known as TSC, represents a prevalent and high-risk complication frequently encountered in the context of tonsillectomy procedures. A considerable body of research has been dedicated to examining various risk factors associated with post-tonsillectomy bleeding. The occurrence of secondary bleeding following tonsillectomy is influenced by numerous factors, including but not limited to age, gender, recent infections, hematological parameters, intraoperative blood loss, and postoperative blood pressure. Nevertheless, the examination of this subject matter revealed a limited number of statistically significant factors associated with the occurrence of post-tonsillectomy bleeding. The postoperative hemorrhage rate following tonsillectomy ranges from 0.3% to 13.9%. Hopkins et al. (year) have demonstrated that there is a potential increase in the frequency of bleeding by a maximum of 18%. The observed hemorrhage rate in our study was 2.7 percent. Transient synovitis of the hip (TSK) exhibits a higher prevalence among adults as compared to children. Tomkinson et al. (year) A study conducted by et al. examined the serial tonsillectomy outcomes of a sample size of 17,680 individuals. The findings indicated that patients who were older than 12 years had a greater likelihood of experiencing bleeding compared to those who were 12 years of age or younger. The prevalence of this rate was 7.8% among adults and 0.14% among children. The findings of our study revealed a higher incidence of bleeding in adults compared to children. The likelihood of experiencing bleeding events is positively correlated with advancing age. The onset of bleeding is not influenced by timing. The term "primary bleeding" refers to bleeding that takes place within a 24-hour timeframe, while "secondary bleeding" refers to bleeding that occurs after this initial 24-hour period.

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Restriction

The research is limited to scientific research that has been previously conducted around the world and reported in the literature.

Notifications

Evaluation: evaluated by internal and external consultants.

Conflict of interest: the authors declared no conflict of interest regarding this article.

Financial support: the authors did not report any financial support related to this article.

Ethical statement

Publishing ethics of current science journal; it is a national-based scientific journal that aims to ensure that scientific research and publications are carried out in accordance with basic

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principles such as honesty, openness, objectivity, respect for the findings and creations of others, and works to achieve this, aiming to achieve these principles in the field of health sciences. The criteria of the declaration of Helsinki were considered.

References

- Alan D, Kornblut A. Non neoplastic diseases of the tonsils and adenoids. In: Paparella M, Shumrick DA, Gluckman JL, Meyerhof WL (eds). Otorhinolaryngology. WB Saunders Company, 1991;3:2129-47.
- Bicknell PG. Role of adenotonsillectomy in the management of pediatric ear, nose, and throat infections. *Pediatr Infect Dis J* 1994; 13:75-78.
- Blakley BW. Post-tonsillectomy bleeding: how much is too much? *Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg* 2009; 140(3): 288-290.
- Blakley BW. Post-tonsillectomy bleeding: how much is too much? *Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg* 2009; 140(3): 288-290.
- Broadman LM, Patel RI, Feldman BA, Sellman GL, Milmo G, Camilon F. The effect of peritonsillar infiltration on the reduction of intraoperative blood loss and posttonsillectomy pain in children. *Laryngoscope* 1989; 99: 578-581.
- Brodsky L, Moore L, Stanievich JF, Ogra PL. The immunology of tonsils in children: the effect of bacterial load on the presence of B and T cell subsets. *Laryngoscope* 1988; 98:93-98.
- Carmody D, Vamadevan T, Cooper S. Post tonsillectomy hemorrhage. *J Laryngol Otol* 1982; 96: 635-638.

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**THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING
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CURRENT SCIENCE

- Catlin FI, Grimes WJ. The effect of steroid therapy on recovery from tonsillectomy in children. Arch Otolaryngol Head Neck Surg 1991; 117: 649-652.
- Cotton R. Nasopharyngeal stenosis. Arch Otolaryngol 1985; 111: 146-148.
- Cowan DL, Hibbert J. Acute and chronic infection of the pharynx and tonsils. In Hibbert J, editors. Laryngology and head and neck surgery. Vol 5. Oxford-Boston: Butterworth-Heinemann;1997. p.17.
- Crysdale W, Russel D. Complications of tonsillectomy and adenoidectomy in 9409 children observed overnight. Can Med Assoc J 1986;135: 1139-1142.
- Friedman M, Tanyeri H. Clinical Predictors of Obstructive Sleep Apnea. Laryngoscope 2009;109(12):1901-1907
- Handler S, Miller L, Richmond K, Baranak C. Post-tonsillectomy
- Har-El G, Nash M. Tonsillectomy, and adenoidectomy, In: Kreps Y, Ossoff R, ed. Complications in head and neck surgery. Philadelphia: Saunders, 1991. p. 75-98.
- hemorrhage: incidence, prevention, and management. Laryngoscope 1986; 96: 1243-1247.
- Hopkins C, Geyer M, Topham J. Post-tonsillectomy haemorrhage: a 7-year retrospective study. Eur Arch Otorhinolaryngol 2003; 260(8): 454-455.
- Kavanagh KT, Beckford NS. Adenotonsillectomy in children: Indications and contraindications. South Med J. 1994; 81(4): 507-511.
- Kornblut AD. A traditional approach to surgery of the tonsils and adenoids. Otolaryngol Clin North Am 1987; 20(2): 349-363.

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Kotecha B, O'Leary G, Bradburn J, Darowski M, Gwinnut CL. Pain relief after tonsillectomy in adults. Clin Otolaryngol 1991; 16: 345-349.

Kritensen S, Tveteras K. Post-tonsillectomy haemorrhage: a retrospective

McClelland L, Jones NS. Tonsillectomy: haemorrhaging ideas. J Laryngol Otol 2005; 119(10): 753-758

McClelland L, Jones NS. Tonsillectomy: haemorrhaging ideas. J Laryngol Otol 2005; 119(10): 753-758

Mortality after tonsil surgery, a population study, covering eight years and 82,527 operations in Sweden. Eurarch

Orzac E. Medical care of the child patient before and after adenoidectomy and tonsillectomy. NY State J Med 1956; 56: 886-887.

Ostvoll E, Sunnergren O, Ericsson E, Hemlin C, Hultcrantz E, Odhagen E, et al.

Ostvoll E, Sunnergren O, Ericsson E, Hemlin C, Hultcrantz E, Odhagen E, et al. Mortality after tonsil surgery, a population study, covering eight years and 82,527 operations in Sweden. Eurarch

Oswalt C, Gates G, Holmstorm F. Pulmonary edema as a complication of acute airway obstruction. JAMA 1977; 238: 1833-1835.

Paradise JL, Bluestone CD, Bachman Z, et al. Efficacy of tonsillectomy for recurrent Throat infections in severely affected children: results of parallel randomised and Nonrandomised clinical trials. N Engl J Med 1984;310:6749.

Parker DA, Gibben KP, Noyelle RM. Syrup formulation for posttonsillectomy analgesia. J Laryngol Autologous 1986; 100: 1055-1060.

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**THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING
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- Rasmussen N. Complications of tonsillectomy and adenoidectomy. *Otolaryngol Clin North Am* 1987; 20(2): 383-390.
- Rasmussen N. Complications of tonsillectomy and adenoidectomy. *Otolaryngol Clin North Am* 1987; 20(2): 383-390.
- Raut V, Bhat N, Kinsella J, Toner JG, Sinnathuray AR, Stevenson M. Bipolar scissor versus cold dissection tonsillectomy: a prospective, randomized, multi-unit study. *Laryngoscope* 2001; 2001: 2178-2182.
- Roy A, De la Rosa C, Vecchio Y. Bleeding following tonsillectomy: a study of electrocoagulation and ligation techniques. *Arch otolaryngol* 1976; 102:9-10.
- Saleh HA, Cain AJ, Mountain RE. Bipolar scissor tonsillectomy. *Clin Otolaryngol Allied Sci* 1999; 24(1): 9-12.
- Siodlak MZ, Gleeson MJ, Wengraf CL. Post-tonsillectomy secondary haemorrhage. *Ann R Coll Surg Engl* 1985; 67: 167-168.
- Stage J, Jensen JH, Bonding P. Posttonsillectomy hemorrhage and analgesics. *Clin Otolaryngol* 1988; 13: 201-204.
- study 1150 operations. *Clin Otolaryngol* 1984; 9: 347-350.
- Tami G, Parker G, Taylor R. Post-tonsillectomy bleeding: an evaluation of risk factors. *Laryngoscope* 1987; 97: 1307-1311.
- Tomkinson A, Harrison W, Owens D, Harris S, McClure V, Temple M. Risk for postoperative hemorrhage following tonsillectomy. *Laryngoscope* 2011; 121(2): 279-288.
- Watters CH, Patterson CC, Mathews HML, Campbell W. Diclofenac sodium for posttonsillectomy pain in children. *Anaesthesia* 1988; 43: 641-643.

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Weighill JS, Proops DW, Jeffries D, Brandrick J. Pain relief following tonsillectomy. J Laryngol Otol 1986; 100: 307-311.

Windfuhr JP. Lethal post-tonsillectomy hemorrhage. Auris Nasus Larynx 2003; 30(4)

Windfuhr JP. Lethal post-tonsillectomy hemorrhage. Auris Nasus Larynx 2003; 30(4)

Ying MD. Immunological basis of indications for tonsillectomy and adenoidectomy. Acta Otolaryngol (Stockh) 1988; 454: 279-285.

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